

The Study of the Traditional Culture of the Salon Nationals

Tin Tin Aung*

Abstract

The Salon nationals are those who were struggling for their existence by fishing, catching leeches, cutting barnacles, finding birds nests, diving pearls. The Salon nationals are the most skillful persons in diving. It is learnt in ancient time even the newly child was thrown into the sea. In ancient time the Salon nationals used not to wear shirts but only wore longyis. At present, with the development of the modern era and with the encouragement and directions of the State Government the Salon nationals has developed in knowledge and view and has begun to wear the full national dress. Since ancient time a Salon male has the right to marry more than one woman. The wealthy people used to practice the polygamy custom more though marriage is conducted by the consent of parents, they have the right divorce. The marriage conduct has controlled marriage to reduce divorce and commitment of his conduct. In ancient time the Salon national did not used to bury the corpse in the ground, but abandoned it by putting on a scaffold build up on tree in an island. At present they have begun to bury the corpses. Therefore, with an intention not to gradually disappear of Salon nationals residing in the archipelagos in lower Myanmar, it is proposed that the plan should be laid down and implemented by the Government of the Union of Myanmar.

Taninthayi Division, in the southernmost part of Myanmar, constituted of three Districts, namely the Dawei District, Myiek District and Kawthaung District. Myeik District is the one which is situated at the southernmost part of Taninthayi Division at the sea beach. It is surrounded by Bay of Bengal in the west, Republic of Malaysia in the south, Republic of Thailand in the east and Dawei District in the north. The Myeik archipelago in the north constituted of over eight hundred small islands along the coast. The area of the District is 11325 square miles.¹

The islands and townships inhabited by Salon nationals in the Myeik and Kawthaung Districts are Myeik Township, Kyunzu Township, Palaw Township, Doon island, Kawthoung Township, Zardetgyi island, Bokebyin Township, Lanpi island, Makyonekalet village, Nyaungwi village and a small number of Salon nationals are found in Kunmway village, Maeing village etc.²

The salon nationals live onboard the boats by roaming in the sea. The dialect they use to communicate is the Austic group of Language.³ There are the Austro Asiatic language used on land and Austro-nesion Language used in water front in Austic Tribe, Mons, Palaungs, Wa and Khamers are included in those who use the land Austro Asaitic Language and the Indonesian, the Malays and Salons are included in the tribes in those who use the marine Austro-nesian Language. Out of those nationals, as the marine tribes are more ancient than land tribes, salons are more ancient people than Mons.⁴

Whereas there are three types of Languages in Austronition Language, the Malay and Salon are included in Indonesian tribe. Therefore, the type of language used by the Salons in

¹ မြန်မာ့စွယ်စုံကျမ်း၊ အတွဲ(၁၀)၊(Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol. X), Yangon, Sarpaybeikan Press, 1962, pp.1-2.

² Tin Yi, Daw, Professor, ဆလုံတိုင်းရင်းသားတို့၏ လူမှုစီးပွားဘဝ (The Social and Economic life of Salon Nationals), Yangon, Universities Press, 2004, p. 1 (Hereafter cited as Social and Economic Life).

³ Pe Maung Tin, U, ဘာသာလောကကျမ်း (Treatise on Religious Life), Yangon Translation Society, 1958, p. 33.

⁴ Major Bashin, စစ်ရေး၊ နိုင်ငံရေး၊ လူမှုရေးဆိုင်ရာ စာတမ်းများ (Thesis on Military, Politics and Social Affairs), Yangon, Bagan Book House, 1968, pp. 300-301.

* Dr., Assistant Lecturer, Department of History, Dagon University

Myeik District is found to be similar to Malays vocabulary.⁵ There are various diversity of concepts relating to the Salon national tribes and the matters how they had entered into Myanmar. It is presumed in various ways, and it is believed by some that a clan from Indonesia and Malay tribe has settled down in Myeik archipelago after they had evacuated to escape the other tribes provocations, influence and suppressions and some people assume that the Salon are the descendents of Malays because the Language they use is similar to Malay nationals language.⁶ Lousis had written in his thesis that Salons does not constitute in the three large national tribes of Tibeto-Myanmar, Monkhamer, and Thai-Chinese groups but they are the lineage of Malay nationals.⁷

J.P. Andrew also stated that the Salon nationals are a tribe who had settled down by establishment of own state, but seem to be the nationals who had evacuated from their original land of Sumatra due to the attack by the Malays.⁸ Though there are diversity of concepts in view of the Salons fear or trust on other nationals except themselves and isolation nature of them till today. It is concluded that, they had to take safe refuge in Myeik archipelago by evacuation from one place to another as they had suffered from the attacks by other tribes.⁹ At present the Salon national tribes not only reside in Myanmar but also in Thailand, Phillipines, Indonesia, Malaysia, etc in all over the Malay Peninsula together with similar tribes. According to a French scholar studying the Salon national tribe, the Salon existed since B.C. 2000 and seemed to have transferred from Chinese territory and had transferred from Taiwan penisular.¹⁰

The terms Salon is the word used by Myanmars. In Malay Peninsula they are known as Orang Bassin and the Thais call them as Chaunan. At present it is noticed that Salons are no longer called as Salons but the word Thaipai, which means the new Thai is used instead.¹¹ But, they themselves call them by the name of Mawkin, which represent the people soaked in sline water.¹²

The physical features of the Salon nationals are usually with medium size forehead, thick eyebrows, round face, broad chins, flat nose and thick lips. Their faces are similar to those of Polynesian tribes members who reside in Pacific islands.¹³ As they are always in touch with sline sea water, though dark hairs are strong, has turned reddish. Though their complexion is white at the time of birth, had become bone dried and languid due to regular contact with sea salt water. As for the body structure they are thin and dwarf. For the present time their

⁵ White, Walter Graing, *The Sea Gypsies of Malay an account of the momadic Mawken People of the Mergui Archipelago, with a description of their way of living custom, Habits, Boat, Occupation Etc*, London, Secley Services and Co Ltd, 1922, p. 56.

⁶ Kyaw Soe, ဆလုံရိုးရာ၊ ဆလုံစရိုက် (Salon tradition, Salon habit), Yangon, Bo Bo Press, 1968, pp. 36-37. (Here after cited as Salon tradition, Salon habit).

⁷ မြန်မာ့စွယ်စုံကျမ်း၊ အတွဲ(၄) (Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol IV), Yangon, Sarpaybeikman Press, 1962, p. 129. (Here after cited as Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol IV).

⁸ Andrew, J.P., *Burma Gazetteer, Mergui District, Vol.A*, Rangon, Government Printing and Stationary, 1960, reprint, p. 9 (Here after cited as BGMD).

⁹ ယဉကျေးမှု/အနုပညာဂျာနယ်အတွဲ(၁)၊ အမှတ်(၄)၊ (Culture and Art Journal, Vol.1, No. 4, 29, January, 2014, p. 25. (Here after cited as Culture and Art Journal).

¹⁰ Pho Kyar, U, “မြိတ်မြို့သွားခြင်း”၊ ဦးစိုးကျားဆောင်းပါးပေါင်းချုပ် (Travel to Myeik, Complete Articles of U Pho Kyar), Yangon Chindwin Press, 1975, p. 214.

¹¹ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 42.

¹² Ahmar, Daw Ludu, သတင်းကြီးတဲ့ချင်းတွင်းခရီး (The famous Chindwin Journey), Kyeepwarye book House, Mandalay, 1981, pp. 5-6. (Here after cited as The famous Chindwin Journey)

¹³ Social and Economic Life, pp. 5-6.

structure had developed and the height of the Salons males is from 5' 2" to 5' 6" and that of the females is 5' 4".¹⁴

Salon family

Modern Salon national

Diving of a Salon national

Though the features of the Salon nationals are rough by the form, it is noticed that the form of the body and mental character very much in the opposite because they are so kind, honest, much scared, easy to have trust and desire to associate between groups.¹⁵ Relating to the dress of Salon nationals, it is described at the time of British Rule, they are not found to dress while staying home or on board the boat, except when they are going out somewhere.

As it is impossible to make weaving as they are not settled down in one permanent place they used to exchange in barter system from Chinese and Malay merchants for their clothing. In ancient times the Salon nationals used not to wear shirts, but only wore longyis. The elderly women did not wear blouse but only wore the longyis wrapped above their breast. Similarly, the children were also unable to wear clothes but stayed naked.¹⁶

Modern Salon family

Ancient Salon nationals

At present, with the development of the modern era and with the encouragement and directions of the State Government the Salon national has developed in knowledge and views and has begun to wear the full national dress. The males has begun to wear long and short pants. They also began to wear batik pattern longyis. The women not only began to wear womens blouses but also wear shirts and T shirts.¹⁷ There the reasons for the Salons not to wear clothes is not for the traditional customs but stayed as savages but due to shortage of wearing apperals. Later it is found that their culture had developed with having more relation with Myanmars and had begun to wear clothes.

In 1911 the British Government made attempted to collect the census for specific number of Salon nationals. For compilation of census figures even some Myanmars and Salon nationals were used. According to the collected statements the total number Salon nationals

¹⁴ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 74.

¹⁵ Ibid, pp. 97-98.

¹⁶ Social and Economic Life, pp. 6-7.

¹⁷ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 74.

residing in the area from the Dawei Island in the north to the St. Methew Island in the south were above 6000.¹⁸ With the anxiety that the Salons may gradually disappear due to climate pressure and other tribes disturbances. Major Broad wood, the Deputy Commissioner of Myeik issued an Act to protect the Salon nationals.¹⁹

But as Salons, by nature are not accustomed for permanent settlement, they continued to wander in the sea. In the rainy season they used to take refuge from rain in groups in long post huts along the sea coast. As it is too expensive and difficult to take census on them, the job was done together with other actions. Their population according to the census taken in 1931 was 1828 persons. They usually settled down in Dawei archipelago, Myeik archipelago, Boakpyin and Victoria point.²⁰ At present, as the Salon population is only under one thousand, and as more than five thousand of Salon population had disappeared in a century, the scholars say that important time has come to protect the Salon population.²¹

Kaban Boat

Kaban (or) Traditional Salon House

View in the Traditional Salon House

Salon nationals are not used to permanent settlement and moving in small boats from one island another and they name their boats as 'Kaban' in their language. Kaban is a boat bound with cane strips and its roof is the one woven with Dhani (nipa palm) leaves. They used to use these boats as their homes.²² Later a mangrove tree with about a length of twenty five feet is cut to make a boat. Then two sides of walls are made with a kind of buoyant and cock like wood called Yindan up to two to three feet height. The boat decks were used to make with large Wabos, the *Dendrocalamus giganteus*. After making the boat deck, a small hut is built at the astern of the boat.²³ The Salons live with their families onboard those boats. Based on the sea, they live by roaming in the sea or on the sea shore. In the rainy season or when storms breakout, they used to take refuge on large or small islands and on the beach by building up long post houses.²⁴

But as they are not used to stay for more than a week in one place, houses are not built up strongly, but built in prefabricated form and lived. It is said that some of them are not building a separated house, but detach the house from the boat and use them as temporary house. According to Mr. Benjamin who had stayed for a considerable time with Salon tribes, the Salons used to live for a short while on the beaches and islands by building temporary huts. It is amazing to find that their houses are dismantled within 15 minutes. They usually stay onboard boats and give birth to children onboard the boats.²⁵

¹⁸ Culture and Art Journal, p. 25.

¹⁹ Salon tradition, Salon habit, pp. 84-85.

²⁰ Bennison, J.J, Census of India, 1931, Vol. XI, Office of the Superintendent Government Printing and Stationary, Rangoon, Burma, 1933, p. 190.

²¹ Culture and Art Journal, p. 25.

²² Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol. IV, p. 130.

²³ B.G.M.D, Vol. A, pp. 9-10.

²⁴ Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol. IV, p. 130.

²⁵ B.G.M.D, Vol. A, p. 9.

View of Salon Talun Village

View of Salon Kawhnyaw Village

View of Salon Nyaungwi Village

At present some the Salon national have settled down on beaches by building up villages. Zardetgyi Island is the largest one in Kawthaung township and Palawkakyanto is the second largest one. St. Paul Island is situated next to the Palawkarkyanlo Island. The old Salon villages, Tarpoo Village and Tarpaw Village, are situated on St. Paul Island. There were about 12 houses. In 1990, the Salon from that villages transferred to Talun and Kawhnyaw villages. The Talun Salon Village is situated in the northwest of Zardetgyi Island. In that place Salons had taken rest since many years before the Navy base was stationed. At present houses with wooden plank walls and floors are being built. Those who have not enough money built their house build with bamboo walls and floor and dhani roof. No rooms are formed. There are 96 houses and 505 populations in Talun Salon Village. Kawhnyaw Salon Village is about a half mile away from Talun Village and situated in Zardetgyi Island. There are 40 families and 156 populations in Kawhnyaw Village.²⁶

Nyaungwi is a large island and there were about four to five huts in the southeast of the island in which the Salon nationals lived in rainy season for 6 years. In that place there is a small creek with running fresh water flowing into the island. As it is an island with the fresh water supply and present Salon are permanently settling down and 18 Salon families with a population of nearly 70 people are living there.²⁷

A Salon House in Nyaungwi Village

View of Salon Makyonekalet Village

Developing Central Street in Makyonekalet Village

Makyonekalet Village is situated near Lanpi Island. It is a village formed with 31 families with 125 populations. In ancient times, long post houses are dismantled in summer and winter and taken onboard boats to wherever they go. When the weather worsened they built up the long pothouses on land wherever they find themselves and lived there. Some of them do not take away the long post houses but left them there. Those long post houses are occupied by new comers.²⁸ At present the small long post houses are built opposite to each

²⁶ Social and Economic Life, p. 2, 3, 12.

²⁷ Sein Myo Myint, မြိတ်ကျွန်းစုအလှများဆီသို့, (Towards the Beauty of Myeik Archipelago), Sarbeilawka Book House, Yangon, 2010, p. 129. (Here after cited as Towards the Beauty of Myeik Archipelago)

²⁸ Social and Economic Life, pp. 108-109.

other along the coast and there is a plank passage in the middle. There are no doors in the huts and are those with roofs, walls and bamboo floors.²⁹

Mangrove forests of Lanpi Island

A school donated by Ma Ohmar in Makyonkalet Village

The long range of island called Lanpi is situated close to Makyonekalet Village in the east. The mangrove trees from Lanpi Island are not dwarf ones like those which grow along Ayeyawaddy river and around Myeik. The mangrove trees from Lanpi Island are very high and their root structure are large. The shoots of the roots emerge through the surface along the beach like many feet. The Lanpi Island is fixed and protected as National Natural Garden.³⁰ The Lanpi Island is one of tourist attractions and the coral reefs, many wild lives, a verity birds, different species of fish and lobsters could be seen. There are 25 Salon national families with 116 members.³¹

Though the dialect used by Salon national is thought to be related to that of Malay as it contain many Malay words, later the researchers assumed that the Salons dialect is closely related to Kham dialect of Campuchia. According to the language of Salon nationals the four main types of Lawta, Lbi, Jait, and Dung are found. The Salon nationals, who have most relations with Malay nationals, use the Lawta language which is most similar to Malay language. The Salon nationals from Lanpi Island and Bokeyyin Township use the Jait language more. Lbi language is mostly used by the Salon nationals living around Victoria Cape and those living around Mathew Island. The Salon nationals from around Myeik mostly use the Dung language and it is learnt that the language is the original language of Salon nationals.³²

It is learnt that Salon nationals' literature has appeared since the beginning of 19th century. That literature was invented by American Baptist missionary Mr. Stevens using Roman alphabets; later Dr. D.L. Brayton had copied the draft compiled by Dr. Brayton in 1844. Then, it is learnt that it is printed and published in Mawlamying through American Baptist Christian Mission press under the title 'A Primer of Selong Language'. In Salon literature, the pronunciation of Salon language is exchanged with Roman alphabets consisted of 22 alphabets.³³

At present there is no Salon Literature at all. Only a few Salon children come to attend the Primary School opened by the Navy base in 1976. There were only four students when the school was opened. There were 10 students in 1982, and 7 students in 1987. Self Reliance Primary School led by Major Yin Maung was able to open on 7 November, 1988. At present

²⁹ Ohnmer, Ma, မကြုံကလပ်နှင့် အနီးဝန်းကျင်ဆလုံကျွန်းများ (Makyonekalet and nearby Salon islands), Chotay Than Sabei, 2004, p. 28. (Here after cited as Makyonekalet)

³⁰ Makyonekalet, p. 211.

³¹ Social and Economic Life, p. 109.

³² Salon tradition, Salon habit, pp. 57-58.

³³ Salon tradition, Salon habit, pp. 61-62.

there are 1 Head Mistress, 3 teachers, and 72 students. Anyhow whereas there were no literate Salon children at all, at present they won the chance to learn and has begun little learning.³⁴

The Salon nationals worship on the most exalted god called Tuda. It is believed and accepted that the Tuda god had created various nationals of the world and their customs and habits and the origin of human beings is the Tuda god. The Salon nationals used to worship the spirit called Ahatoi who could create evils on human beings. Therefore, though the Salon nationals have faith on the eternal god they are also animists.³⁵ A wooden spirit shrine pillar of 6'' squares is found at Makyonekaletvillage. At the foot of the pillar the wood is carved and decorated with various colours.³⁶

Report to Lupone spirit by Spirit consort in front of Lupone Spirit Shrine

Paraphernalia used in animist worship

The ancestors' soul worship

The traditionally worshipped spirits in Talun Village and Kawhnyaw Village in Zardetkyi Island in Kawthoung Township is the Lupone spirit in Salon name. Apart from the Lupone spirit, the ancestors' souls are also worshipped. The Salons believed that the Lupone spirit could do good and evil on human beings. There is only one spirit shrine for both villages of Talun and Kawhnyaw. That spirit shrine is situated in the Talun Village. Near the spirit shrine, only three spirit pillars are found.³⁷ The method of worshipping is made by raising the spirit pillar; it is decorated with banners and flags and honoured with the blood of duck, chicken, bird, dolphin, and the games by praying to the spirits. Then, the participants in the nat festival sit one after another and in the pose of boat rowing, and shouting rallying cries, move towards the beach gradually and chase out the devil spirits by shouting out in unity.³⁸ The Salon nationals have to pay homage to their ancestors' souls once in every year, at full moon day's night. They go to the cemetery at about 6 p.m. on the day on which they pay homage to the Lupone spirit.³⁹ In the year 1839, when the Christian missionaries arrive in Myeik District, it was able Baptist 29 Salon nationals.⁴⁰

The Salon nationals, who have continuously practiced animism have now committed into Buddhism. On the 6 November 1970, the Dhammikarama Monastery and the Sutaungpyie peace Pagoda was established and worshipped. The Shwedagon Pagoda, the replica of Yangon Shwedagon Pagoda was built up and being worshipped on Salon island in which the ancient Salons lived, with the directives of the State leaders.⁴¹

³⁴ Social and Economic Life, pp. 111-112.

³⁵ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 50.

³⁶ The Famous Chindwin Journey, p. 179.

³⁷ Social and Economic Life, p. 55.

³⁸ Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol. IV, p. 131

³⁹ Social and Economic Life, p. 56.

⁴⁰ Than Maung Sein, “မြိတ်နှင့်နှစ်ခြင်းသာသနာ” (Myeik and Baptist Religion), Myeik Magazine, 1334, Composers Day, p. 75.

⁴¹ Social and Economic Life, pp. 68-69.

There is no age limit for Salon nationals for their marriage. There is a custom of years long courtship among them. The Salons also take the service of the matchmaker for negotiation of marriage between one another. The matchmaker should be the woman for their family who bore most number of children. As for the Salon nationals, it is not necessary to be rich or educated, in choosing as a marriage partner. It is only the main factor to be able to build a Kaban boat in which they could live. Moreover he also has to possess the skill of diving and fishing. The youths with such skill are liked by the girls and their parents and selected as their bridegroom. When the negotiation is successful the youth himself has to go to the brides home and perform the negotiation and marriage ceremony simultaneously.

The customs of the Salons are closely related to Myanmar's; the habit of handing over a piece of betel quid. If the betel quid is accepted by the brides' side, it is the signal that the parent had agreed on the matter. After the agreement is reached, the bridegroom and his parents go to the bride's home with gold, silver, jewellery, dress and marriage gifts and ask for the bride and bring her home. The father of bridegroom has to serve the bride's parents and the guests with liquor. The village headman or the matchmaker has to solicit the bride's mother with gifts. If the bride's mother accepted, the things are placed on the spirit shrine at the front of the house. That is the gesture that after asking the permission from the parents, to approve it by the nats or the spirits also. At that time a member from the family has to go to forest and cut a tree. For the marriage ceremony the tree is carved as a human body and painted with red and yellow paint and the bridegroom and bride sit near the statue and all other had to dance around them.⁴² Just after marriage the bridegroom had to cut a boat for them. Some of the parents give their children a boat as their marriage gift. Generally the Salon nationals live separately from their parents only after they had their first child, by separate home or boat.⁴³ The patrilocal residence system, in which a bride had to go and stay in her parents in laws home is found in Salons tradition. Since ancient times a Salon male has the right to marry more than one woman. The wealthy people used to practice the polygamy custom more. They used to keep their wives in the same house or onboard the same boat. Sometimes each wife and her children are kept in separate hut and used to go and stay in turn.

Though marriage is conducted by the consent of parents, they have the right divorce. The bride had the right to own the bride price paid by the youth's side. If it the guilt is found on the bridegroom's side, he is liable to pay the fine as much as the brides side claims. If it is guilty on the bride side, they are also liable to pay the fine as much as the bridegroom side claims. The above marriage conduct has controlled marriage to reduce divorce and commitment of his conduct.⁴⁴

The Salon women have to continue with her daily works even after she is married and got pregnant. There is no habit of noting the date of pregnancy and the date of birth.⁴⁵ In ancient times as the Salon nationals stayed onboard Kaban boats roaming in the sea, they had to give birth onboard their boats. At the when they settled down permanently on land due to bad weather, they give birth in the houses on the island. At the time of birth, labour is conducted with the help of the experienced midwives. The spirit consort, Sherman was called and kept ready at the time of birth. The consort had to pray on the Lupon sprint and make requests and offer with liquor litingsence sticks, and candles to be smooth in every way and for easy labour.

⁴² Myanmar Encyclopedia, Vol. IV, p. 131.

⁴³ Social and Economic Life, p. 43.

⁴⁴ Ibid, p. 37, 53.

⁴⁵ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 181.

After giving birth the woman under heat treatment has to go into the sea and take bath. There is also a habit of dipping the child for a while in sea water and bathe. It is learnt that in ancient times the newly born child was to be thrown into the sea. It is told that the intention of doing so is to become a good swimmer, good navigator, and a useful person for the mankind. By doing so, there are some cases in which the child is drowned to death. At present such custom is being gradually diminishing in Talun and Kawhnyaw villages.⁴⁶ The Salon mothers are beginning to use the Disposable Delivery Kit supplied by the UNICEF in their child birth and also having enough preventive medicines. It is noticed that it is possible to give necessary preventive medicines as prescribed by the Department of Health Services.⁴⁷

The child is only given a name after a week or a month. Father's mother has to name if a boy is born and the mother's mother has to give a name if a girl is born. Real fathers and mothers could name their children only when there were no grandfathers and grandmothers. It is also learnt the children are given various names as they like and the child is called as "Ahne" before he was named.⁴⁸

Funeral Service of a Salon national

Spirit pillar of Salon crematory

The Crematory of Salon nationals

In ancient times, the Salon national did not used to bury the corpse in the ground, but abandoned it by putting on a scaffold build up on tree in an island. The island without springs or mountain streams was chosen to abandon the corpses. As that island is not suitable for hunting and it is used as the grave. The goods and materials owned by the dead person are also left near his corpse. If the boat owner, the chief of the household dies the boat is cut into two parts and put the corpse on one part and covered it with another part of the boat.⁴⁹

When they arrived at the grave island, the corpse cover is opened and placed the corpse on the scaffold. The boat owned by him and all his belonging were also left near. By leaving his boat and his belongings it is believed that the dead person could enjoy a wealthy life in his new existence. But such custom has been nearing to total disappearance at the present time. Because, the corpse left on the scaffold was eaten by wild animals, the thieves take away the belongings and the destruction of the scaffolds. At present they have begun to bury the corpses. The corpse is kept from three to five days as they have to wait for the families and parents.

⁴⁶ Social and Economic Life, pp. 47-48.

⁴⁷ Makyonekalet, p. 41.

⁴⁸ Salon tradition, Salon habit, p. 185.

⁴⁹ Salon tradition, Salon habit, pp. 243-244.

The corpses are kept for up to five days if the death is by sickness and for two days in cases of sudden death. There are also the custom to bathe the corpse on the date of burial and soon after death. The corpse is dressed in proper with new clothes. The dead man's corpse is placed on the mat and put into the coffin only when it has arrived. If there is no mat available they cut down the walls from the house and wrapped the corpse with it. Coffin is made by joining the planks and if there are no planks available, planks from the house are taken to make the coffin.

Bathing of the corpse, dressing and making coffin are helped by the neighbours. In ancient times there were the customs to hold the funeral service by leaving the exactly half of the dead persons belongings including gold and silver together with the corpse of the dead person on the scaffold. At present as the Salon nationals has been modernized; they now used to do the funeral service by putting a hair pin for a female and a diving goggle for a male. Some of the Salon nationals used to bury the corpse of the male on rising tide and the corpse on the ebbing tide. Some of the Salon nationals do not bury the corpses on the rising tide but buried on the ebbing tide.⁵⁰

In conclusion, The Salon nationals are those who are struggling for their existence by fishing, catching leeches, cutting barnacles, finding birds' nests, diving pearls. The Salon nationals are the most skilful persons in diving. It is learnt in ancient times even the newly child was thrown into the sea. It is said that doing so is to make the child a man who could dive in water for long and a skilful swimmer in sea water and a good navigator.

The type of the dress of the Salon nationals in ancient times were, the male Salon people did not use to wear shirts but they only wear the longyis. The females have no blouse but only wore longyis to cover the breast. At present, in accordance with the development of modern times, with the aid and encouragement and directions of the State Government, the Salon nationals have been developed in their knowledge and views and have been wearing the full dress. As the Salon nationals are struggling for existence in all the time since their birth, they were unable to learn school education. Though they literature in ancient times, it had disappeared gradually as they were struggling for their living and being unable to learn. At present as the Primary School is opened and taught since 1976, the Salon national children have the chance to learn and had learnt a little.

In religious sector also, those Salon nationals who had continuously practiced animism have now turned into Buddhist and a replica of the Shwedagon Pagoda is built up in Salon island with the directions of the State Leaders from the States Peace and Development Council. Therefore, with an intention not to gradually disappear of the Salon nationals residing in the archipelagos in lower Myanmar, and for the development of their social, economic and cultures to improve in various sectors, it is proposed that the plans should be laid down and implemented by the Ministry of Frontier Area and National Races Development and the Government of the Union of Myanmar.

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